

from alcohol as needles, m. p. 198°, yield 1.8 g. It has slight camphoric smell. It is much less soluble than either thiocamphor or thioborneol. It is less sublimable than thiocamphor. [Found: C, 70.6; H, 10.3; S, 18.81; M. W. in benzene (cryoscopic), 335.6. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{34}S_2$: C, 71.01; H, 10.06; S, 18.93 per cent. M. W., 338]

In conclusion, my sincerest thanks are due to Sir P. C. Ray for his kind interest in the investigation and also for giving me facilities in his laboratory.

PALIT LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received April 18, 1934

The Formation of Amides from Nitriles by the Action of Hydrogen Peroxide.

By L. McMASTER AND C. R. NOLLER.

In a recent paper Murray and Cloke (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2749) report the advantage of using a solvent such as methanol, ethanol or acetone in the Radziszewski reaction. The same conclusion was reached by us a few years ago during the course of a fairly detailed study of the optimum conditions for this reaction. Because of the inaccessibility of these data, it is thought desirable to briefly summarise them here.

In general, the hydrogen peroxide was added to a weighed portion of the nitrile and sufficient 95% ethanol added to bring the nitrile into solution. Sufficient 6N-sodium hydroxide was added to make the solution alkaline to litmus after which it was kept at 60° for 4 hours. If necessary, more sodium hydroxide was added during the course of the reaction to keep the mixture alkaline. The mixture was then cooled, neutralised with sulphuric acid, evaporated to dryness and either extracted with chloroform or crystallised from water. The amides were finally purified to constant melting point. In a few cases no ethanol was used but the nitrile was stirred with the hydrogen peroxide. The best conditions as determined by from two to eight experiments for each nitrile, using 3, 6, 12 and 30% hydrogen peroxide, are given in the following table.

Conditions and yields for the conversion of nitriles into amides by the action of hydrogen peroxide.

Nitrile.	Wt. of nitrile.	Amt. and conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Amt. of 95% C ₂ H ₅ OH.	Crude amide.	M.p. of purified amide (cor.).
Propio-	1.045 g.	10 c.c. 12%	None	49.6%	80.1°
<i>n</i> -Butyro-	1.050	20 6	None	64.9	114.6
<i>n</i> -Valero-	1.000	10 6	10 c.c.	62.5	104.1
<i>iso</i> Valero-	1.045	10 6	10	56.5	135.4
Phenylaceto-	1.095	20 6	20	59.5	159
Diphenylaceto-	1.000	5 30	10	69.0	166.5
α -Phenylcinnamo-	1.000	10 12	25	83.0	202.6
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzo-	1.000	25 6	None	80.4	176.5
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzo-	1.000	25 6	None	91.2	201.6
<i>o</i> -Tolu-	1.100	5 30	10	93.0	141.5
<i>m</i> -Tolu-	1.368	5 30	10	84.8	93.8
Piperonylo-	1.000	50 3	None	97.4	168.6
<i>o</i> -Nitropiperonylo-	0.500	10 12	None	85.4	199.6

The reaction with *o*-tolunitrile has been carried out on a much larger scale (88 g.) with equally satisfactory results ("Organic Syntheses," Vol. 13, p. 94).

It is of interest to note that the effect of alkali in this reaction is not merely to bring about a decomposition of the hydrogen peroxide in the presence of the amide, but that the hydroxyl ion is apparently a necessary catalyst for the reaction. Hydrogen peroxide in concentrations up to 30% when decomposed catalytically by manganese dioxide, freshly precipitated cobaltic hydroxide, cobaltic oxide or nickelic oxide, has no effect on neutral solutions of propionitrile or *o*-nitrobenzonitrile at temperatures up to 100°.